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INFORMATION LITERACY NEEDS IN REMOTE AREAS (CASE STUDY ON THE ISLAND OF ACEH)

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to know the needs of information literacy in remote areas of Aceh Island. The method in this study is a qualitative research method with a direct approach to the source of research informant namely Pulo Aceh community, long time this research was conducted for four months in Pulo Aceh. The result of this research is that the people of Pulo Aceh should get the same rights in fulfilling the needs of information, they also have the same needs of information literacy as other communities. Therefore, libraries need to pay attention to areas that are left behind in the dissemination of information. The library as an information center should have an effort to reach isolated areas such as Pulo Aceh. Libraries must provide service information regardless of ethnic, racial, geographic location, and other backgrounds. The role of the library in fulfilling the information needs to Pulo Aceh community is more noted and prioritized as an isolated area. With the fulfillment of information needs they are able to develop competitive with other communities to improve information literacy, but more advanced technological development in order to provide comprehensive information services to remote areas. So they can get information quickly, and relevant and adapted to the needs of the community Pulo Aceh.

Keywords: *Information, Information Literacy, and Libraries.*

Introduction

Globalization of information very rapidly in the information age today have such a huge impact on either side of the positive or negative for the seekers of information. Impact plus was the opening of various kinds of information so that information seekers have the opportunity to get the information widely. More over the downside i.e. because it is too large number of available information, information seekers are often stuck with information that does not comply with the requirements or even obtain information that is wrong.

Therefore, globalization information is becoming a major challenge for the libraries in meeting the needs for information for information seekers. Coupled with the diverse information seekers are tailored to their needs. The presence of references is great wealth which can be utilized by optimally information seekers. It is seen from the role of libraries as information services and service for the wider community. The library needs to be supported by the ability of techniques that are efficient and effective in the use of means (services) library to meet the information needed by the wearer, as the ability to search for information is not as important with the information itself.

Information literacy is the responsibility of the library to provide to society, skills in using other sources of information both in print and non-print (electronic form). The skills that make a society become familiar against other sources of information

and technology contained in the library. So that in the future they can utilize the library easily, quickly and confidently.

There is an enormous growth in programmes in libraries that offer training and support for Information Literacy, but still a strong tendency for them to be driven by the priorities of librarians. The reader can assess the justice of this claim from several international surveys or by a trawl of the Web using obvious search terms. The programmes tend to be predominantly in academic institutions, and consist of lectures and practical work with a strongly didactic character.¹

The library hasn't been able to provide a growing source of information and is required by users and serve the community users with professional, then being able to compete with the institutions engaged in the field of other information. In a world that is moving fast paced every organization who manages information, including libraries have struggled to able to survive or exist.²

The library is an institution that serves as the principal source of information (Source of Information). Managers, manage, package, and disseminate such information. Librarians

¹ Andretta in Paul Sturges and Almuth Gasting, *Information Literacy as A Human Right*. Volume 60, Issue 3. *International Journal of Libraries and Information Studies* Published Online: 2010-11-04 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1515/libr.2010.017>.

² Suwarno, Wiji, *Organization Information the library (Approximation theory and practice)*, (Jakarta: the King of Grafindo Prsada, 2016). Page. 8.

also provide continuous service, and are always ready to help a user (Users) who seek and need the information.³

In order to meet the needs of remote communities for information literacy then librarians need to be more active again. So, literacy information to be spread evenly to all walks of life. Especially for remote areas such as Pulo Aceh is often constrained in getting that information literacy needs of information seekers.

The State has been hampered by the presence of Pulo Aceh that is difficult to reach by road. One alternative in meeting the needs of information literacy is by way of the library should utilize line ship to reach remote areas of Pulo Aceh. But this is not an effective alternative in meeting the needs of the literacy needs of information on Pulo Aceh, caused by obstacles for librarians in the adjust the State of the sea. Therefore, the Pulo Aceh into a region lagging behind in obtaining the information fast, relevant, and up-to-date.

Therefore, the mastery librarian as professionals in the package information and distribute it to a remote community in meeting the needs of information becomes a challenge. On the other side of a librarian sued could realize the library community, to allow humanist able to access needed information independently, The problem in this research is that the, how

³ Fatmawati, Endang, *The Art of Library; Essay about the art of Nourishing Ties Manage Library*, (Semarang: Penebit University of Diponegoro, 2010). Page. 163.

information literacy needs in remote areas of Aceh Island. The purpose of this research is, knowing the needs of information literacy in remote areas of Aceh Island.

Some supporting references that researchers make as a basic reference in conducting this research are as follows; Information literacy as a human right, Remote library users-needs and expectations, Information literacy in the reference environment: preparing for the future, and Information literacy in practice: engaging public library workers in rural South.

From some of the above article titles discuss the needs of information literacy both in the form of expectations and needs of public libraries for certain areas in fulfilling the needs of information literacy for the public in general. However, this research is focused on fulfilling information needs in one area, namely Pulo Aceh. Researchers selected this area as the focus of research seen from the location of isolated areas and not fulfilled adequate information for the community in Pulo Aceh.

Methods that can help and analyze in the problems that will be researched.⁴ Research methods are a scientific way to get data with specific objectives and usability.⁵ This research is qualitative research using a descriptive approach to analysis, a more emphasized approach in the process of deductive and inductive approval as well as on analysis in the dynamics of

⁴ Soekidjo Notoatmodjo, *Health Research Methodology* (Jakarta: Rineka Cipta, 2005), Page. 19.

⁵ Sugiyono, *research method of administration* (Bandung: Alfabeta, 2006), Page. 1.

relationships between observed phenomena, By using scientific logic.⁶

Therefore, a descriptive approach aims to observe, understand and describe the symptoms or social phenomena that occur by classifying a number of variables that pertain to the unit to be researched. Nonetheless, the literature in certain matters remains, especially with regard to the focus of research.

Discussion

Geographical Pulo Aceh

Pulo Aceh is a subdistrict in Aceh Besar Regency, Aceh province, Indonesia. Pulo Aceh is the area of the administration of level III located in Indonesia.

Need for Information

The development of science and technology is so rapid today have an impact to the development of the needs for information. Increasingly fast development of the information, the number and diversity of its shape, the more confusing the community in an attempt to find information. The various information needs and information generated, at a certain time or period, or with a specific purpose or direction and others.

The library as an information centre and the community that need information like the two sides of the coin are

⁶ Saifuddin Azwar, *Research Methods* (Yogyakarta: Offset Learning Library, 1998), Page. 5.

interconnected which cannot be separated. It can be realized where kala library is ready to serve with an adequate source of information. While the public is able to understand, want to live/, and interpret the importance of information in her everyday.⁷

Sulistyo Basuki-add library based by the thought that the service information to users is the main goal of the services of the library. The satirical reflected on Ranganathan's five principles as the Foundation of the law of library science, among others, are:

1. The Information is for use. This reflects the principle that the information is to be utilized as fully as possible. Information that is not used is wasteful.
2. Every information user his/her information maintenance. The information is for all people without discriminating based on race, ethnic origin, skin colour, age, and education background.
3. Every piece of information its users. User information is entitled to the information. information becomes a commodity in the information society.
4. Save the time of information users. Nowadays more and more of the public considers the time is money, so those who get information first could move faster than those who do not have the information.

⁷ Sutarno, *a library and a community*, (Jakarta: Sagung Seto, 2006).
Page. 1.

5. The universe of information is overgrowing. Such information center library and its wearer are growing and changing, emerging sophisticated service claims, and demands of librarians who have Information literacy.

But in fact, the principle above is not fully realized, the dissemination of information only in the category of affordable areas are a priority of the library. But remote areas became the longest move, in the absence of information by spread to remote areas of the community, this was not in accordance with the principle of Ranganatan opinions. Therefore, the Pulo Aceh region is one of the remote isolation in getting maximum information.

The library is expected to improve its information services actively. One of the appropriate measures to tackle it is to ways to further expand the dissemination of information to remote areas such as Pulo Aceh, to be able to meet the need for information, so that the Pulo Aceh is able to membenah myself to moving fast in adjusting both in terms of knowledge and development, UN regions.

The author's observations in the field, it still shows that the existence of the complaints against the fulfillment of the requirement for information on Pulo Aceh. They are always lagging behind both in terms of education, and the development of the region. In this case the author argues library must manifest their desire to improve the aspect of education and development,

UN terrain in a way help them get other sources of information more relevant and Up to date.

The idea of the author in response to fulfilling the information needs of remote areas in Pulo Aceh, libraries need to be fair in giving information to all walks of life. Hence from that good contributions in realizing fair attitude to maximize the dissemination of information in remote areas make it a top priority in meeting the needs of information literacy.

Information Literacy Tutoring

A number of efforts to formulate a better concept and relation on other skills and literacy form. However other educational purposes, including traditional literacy, computer literacy, library skills, and critical thinking skills, information literacy and associated on the basis of further development, literacy appears as a number of obvious skills and key to prosperity in the lives of the increasingly complex information society.⁸

As a discourse in the future, the author of the opinion that information literacy is able to play its role in the information society life in prosper oriented with the development of the times. Although in practice there are also other elements that come into play a role in information literacy. So literacy needs to be

⁸ Widyawan, Rosa, service reference, Pemustaka, Guidance and Information Literacy (LI), services-references-guidance-pemustaka-and-information-literacy-retrieved on 11 September 2017.

developed to evoke the image of libraries in providing information for the public in Pulo Aceh.

Generally the author pointed out that this information literacy essentially must have side concern of the library to be able to remote communities with partners in improving the attractiveness in utilizing information literacy thoroughly and be able to improve the image of the provider information such as library.

Information Society Literacy

Literacy of information well can provide an important relationship between the information society and learning society. Information literacy skills help people to study and learn, to train the various life changes so quickly to revamp the world and requires them to adapt and be flexible with the speed and competence in a way almost imaginable a few years ago.⁹

Then if this community information literacy can create reciprocal changes in society. This information literacy can be packaged in the form of a more practical to be able to berkompetensi in meeting the information needs of remote areas. The library has a very large role for literacy was capable of creating information with the skills possessed by the librarian. As pointed out by Fatmawati in Maslahah there must be three things

⁹ Mustofa, User Education VS. Literacy Information. In <http://digilib.isi-ska.ac.id/?p=499>. Retrieved on October 28, 2017.

to so that libraries can play a role and still exist in the era of information such as:

1. A qualified Librarian (Knowledge, Idea, experience, skills),
2. Support of appropriate technology, and
3. The creation of a culture that either in a library.¹⁰

Did I understand literacy in the information society is a librarian should be more active as a provider/giver information, and even librarians should also could be a carrier of information. to deal with the information age librarians should be able to see the different points of view in addressing the literacy needs of the information society. Candy stated that:

".. Information literacy is not only a response to the demands of the information society, but important set of intellectual achievement that can help in the realization of a society of learning".

Basically this community information literacy is not enough to master the various technologies, as in Aceh still has a lot of Pulo lack and limitation in utilizing the technology. To Pulo Aceh serves the community in getting more information literacy operates to librarians who are able to help provide services that facilitate access to information in accordance with their needs. This effort is a bit much to expect reduced the gap and was able to access the information society literacy mensterakan Pulo

¹⁰ Khoirul, Maslahan, and Nusrotul Hasanah, *Humanism-based library services: library*, Surakarta IAIN, 2013. Page. 51.

Aceh with the community of the city, or provide access to the entire justice society.

The view of the author related to the revelation that with a library of Achmad evenly ground water then negaraa citizens can obtain information to improve the quality of life. While there is information in the library. Thus the rights of citizens for information are met because the Government is Lordship.¹¹

The author's observations in the field, the democratic system in Pulo Aceh community information literacy is still much hope. Because there's less gain equality in acquiring the information faster and more relevant. It became a benchmark for authors that the Government guarantee will be information for the rest of the community only became the selogan only. However, the facts prove there are always gaps in information literacy to suit the needs of remote communities particularly in Pulo Aceh.

Prasetyawan paint the views, on 10 January 1989, The Presidential Commite on Informastion Literacy published a report which in essence emphasizes the importance of information literacy and information literacy to develop opportunities in the the school. The Commission recommends the establishment of the National Forum on Information Literacy, a coalition of 90 national and international organizations. The development is striking in this case is the increased attention to

¹¹ Achmad, et al. The service of love: the embodiment of excellent service ++ library, Jakarta: Sagung Seto, 2012. Page. 30.

the process of teaching. In 1989, the American Library Association Presidential Committee on information Literacy in order to urge the people to develop information literacy to take part in the dynamics of the information society. In the report, formulated as information literacy as the ability to recognize when information is needed; have the ability to acquire, evaluate, and use information effectively, stressed that it was important information literacy for all walks of life.¹²

Furthermore the association of college and research libraries in prasyetawan gives a description of the characteristics about the person who has the capability of information literacy. The person who has the ability of information literacy is they have the ability to:

1. Determine information required
2. Access needs the information effectively and efficiently
3. Evaluate information and its sources critically
4. Combine the information chosen to be a foundation of knowledge
5. Use the information effectively to accomplish a specific goal
6. Knowing the issues of economic, legal, and social surrounding the use of information

The challenges of information society literacy is a contribution in support of the achievement of the Government's

¹² Prasetyawan, Yanuar of Yoga, "Information Literacy and the role of Librarians as agents of Literacy", Proceedings: Discourse of information Literacy. (Semarang (Central Java, FPPTI: 2014). Page. 160.

program to improve equality of information for the entire community, especially remote areas such as Pulo Aceh. They became the main contributor to literacy information for communities and more complex if the librarian has a role to be enhanced helps users to find relevant information in the most appropriate format in a timely fashion (and at a cost that is acceptable to users or funding agencies or both). Can not be denied again, consciously or unconsciously, now no longer seabagai its head librarian information. Information is now everywhere, easy and cheap to get it. Access to information many ways and kinds. So that libraries can effectively disseminate information literacy programs, the need for collaboration with the institution of the library's social habitation, whether it be school, University, region, or Corporation.

Librarians must have knowledge that the information was used as a set of a process. This information is highly contextual. Information cannot be a knowledge if it doesn't fit the context. Information must be obtained from the right people. The effective use of information includes the process of critical thinking and evaluation of the information obtained. It became a cornerstone of the concept of thinking librarians to fight for and distribute information literacy ability.

The Importance of Information Literacy

Mishra Pattah posited in the development of information technology has brought about drastic changes in procurement,

organization, management and dissemination of information.¹³ However, according to Walker and Jones Pattah, technological advances in communication and information is not necessarily ease the process of re-discovery of information, it may even be difficult for search. On the other hand, the development of technology is closely related to a change in attitude or behavior and abilities of users in finding information and using the information that it needs. For some end-users interact directly with information systems is complicated.

The author argues that, hope is able to sense the development of information technology for the remote community be a very difficult thing for them. This fact is evident from the circumstances of those who are still lags behind both in terms of obtaining information as well as in terms of the services of the Government. The growing technological development can not improve literacy information for remote people in Pulo Aceh. Whereas the community is in need of information literacy in order to follow the development of the times.

According to Mishra in Pattah, this happens due to the increased amount of information as well as the quality of information that is not obvious to the user. In addition the information received in a variety of media (multimedia) including images, or text. People also began to question the

¹³ Husaebah, of Sitti P (2014). Information literacy competency: improved information in the learning process. *Journal of the science of Library Archival & Khizanah Al-Hikmah*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp.

validity or authenticity, validity and realibilitas of the information acquired. To make appointment return information into effective and clear, people prosecuted for "information literacy (information literate)", because it required the ability to obtain and manage information (information skills).

Conclusion

Pulo Aceh community should've not discriminatory because it mistreated while they were in the area, they also have the same information literacy needs with other societies. Therefore, the library need to pay attention to areas left behind in the disseminate information.

If you want to be called a library as an information center, the library should have a service that can be accessed by remote areas. The library should provide service information regardless of tribe, race, geographical location, and other background. Thus they are capable of developing competitive with other communities in improving information literacy.

The existence of the community need to be attentive of Aceh Pulo library support information literacy, however the development of a more advanced technology in order to supply a comprehensive information service to remote areas. So that they can feel the information fast, and relevant and tailored to community needs Pulo Aceh.

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